

A postcard from the future: Tools and services from a perfect DMP world

IDCC, 20 Feb 2017
Photo by Rune Askeland on 500px

Machine-actionable DMPs

- Data discovery
- Capacity planning
- Aggregation/integration
- Policy compliance

Program

- 9:05 Demo of INDIGO-Datacloud, Fernando Aguilar Gómez
- 9:20 Demo of life science Data Stewardship wizard, Rob Hooft
- 9:35 Mind map activity
- 10:20 Group discussion
- 10:45 Coffee
- 11:00 Active DMPs vision, Tomasz Miksa
- 11:15 Machine-actionable use cases activity
- 12:15 DMP Roadmap project update
- 12:30 Lunch!

Mind map instructions

1. Describe your day-to-day data management workflow, including systems/software. Write 5–10 high-level activities on sticky notes.
2. Come together in groups of 4–5 and create a mind map.

Discussion

- Which systems/services should connect with DMP tools?
- What can be automated and what will always have to be completed manually?
- Workflows for DMPs: consider pathways to sharing/publishing/discovering...
- How can we bring DMPs closer to data?
- ...

Machine-actionable use cases

1. Interoperability with other systems
2. Utilizing PIDs
3. Institutional use cases
4. Repository use cases
5. Data discovery
6. Evaluation and monitoring
7. Disciplinary tailoring
8. Publishing DMPs

28 responses

SUMMARY

INDIVIDUAL

Accepting responses

Note your top 3 preferences (28 responses)

maDMP use case instructions

1. Take 5–10 min to write as many goals and/or requirements as come to mind on sticky notes.
2. Go around group one-by-one, add a sticky note to the board. Create additional requirements at any point. Repeat until everyone has run out of stickies and passes on their turn.
3. Cluster the requirements into topics and/or sequences.
4. Dot voting to prioritize. Everyone gets 3 dots to place beside high-priority/value items. 1-red, 2-yellow, 3-green
5. Make notes of anything that influences prioritization (e.g., easy/difficult to implement; benefits multiple stakeholders).
6. Report back at the end (1 min lightning round).

DMPRoadmap update

<https://github.com/DMPRoadmap>

DMPRoadmap / roadmap

Watch 14 Star 7 Fork 13

Code Issues 35 Pull requests 0 Projects 1 Wiki Pulse Graphs Settings

Development roadmap

Edit New Page

stephaniesimms edited this page 11 days ago · 9 revisions

Roadmap to MVP

- Migration to Rails v.4.2
- Bring DMP Assistant's internationalization upstream for multi-lingual support
- OAuth link for ORCID
- APIs to create plans, extract guidance, and generate usage statistics
- More robust institutional branding
- Admin controls for assigning admin rights to others
- Add the concept of locales so specific organizations, funders, and templates can be defined and filtered out for certain users/contexts
- Shibboleth support through eduGain
- Export template with guidance
- Flag "test" plans
- Public sharing option > Public DMPs library

Pages 18

Find a Page...

- Home
- About
- Administration
- Branding
- Contributing
- Developer guide
- Development roadmap
- DMPTool steering committee

How we're working

ORCID integration

 University of California Office of the President Signed in as [super_admin@example.com](#)

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Edit profile

Please note that your email address is used as your username. If you change this, remember to use your new email address on sign in.

You can edit any of the details below.

Email *	<input type="text" value="super_admin@example.com"/>
First name	<input type="text" value="Super"/>
Last name	<input type="text" value="Admin"/>
Organisation	<input type="text" value="University of California Offi... x"/>
Language	<input type="text" value="English (UK) x"/>
orcid	Create or Connect your ORCID ID

If you would like to change your password please complete the following fields.

Current password	<input type="password"/>
New password	<input type="password"/>
Password confirmation	<input type="password"/>

ORCID integration

ORCID

DMPTool

has asked for the following access to your ORCID Record

Get your ORCID ID

- Allow this permission until I revoke it.
*You may revoke permissions on your account settings page.
Unchecking this box will grant permission this time only.*

This application will not be able to see your ORCID password, or other private info in your ORCID Record. [Privacy Policy](#).

Sign into ORCID or [Register now](#)

Personal account

Institutional account

Sign in with your ORCID account

Email or ID *

ORCID Password

[Forgotten password?](#)

Deny

Authorize

ORCID integration

Signed in as super_admin@example.com ▾

University of California Office of the President

- View plans
- Create plan
- About
- Future plans
- Help
- Public DMPs
- Change language ▾

Your account has been connected to orcid

Edit profile

Please note that your email address is used as your username. If you change this, remember to use your new email address on sign in.

You can edit any of the details below.

Email *	<input type="text" value="super_admin@example.com"/>
First name	<input type="text" value="Super"/>
Last name	<input type="text" value="Admin"/>
Organisation	<input type="text" value="University of California Offi... x ▾"/>
Language	<input type="text" value="English (UK) x ▾"/>
orcid	<input type="text" value="id https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9129-3790 x"/>

If you would like to change your password please complete the following fields.

Current password	<input type="password"/>
New password	<input type="password"/>

FundRef integration

Signed in as user@organization.org

[About](#) [Public DMPs](#) [View Plans](#) [Create Plans](#)

Create a new plan

Select a funder for customized plan templates and guidance.

Look up your funder

National Aeronautics and Space Administration

USDA - NIFA: National Institute of Food and Agriculture

No funder associated with this plan

Create Plan

Join us for more!

Tuesday, 15:30-16:30, Parallel A3

Next-Generation Data Management Plans: Global, Machine-Actionable, FAIR

Wednesday, 14:00-15:30, Roadmap for DMPs

A demo and update on the DMPRoadmap code, a developer track and DMP support track

Thursday 6th April, 9:30-11:00, Active DMP IG session @ RDA Plenary in Barcelona

More updates and community discussion to set agenda for machine-actionable DMP work